

Fatigue Failure Prediction for Unidirectional Composite Using SFF Model with Entropy Damage Criterion

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Overview

What we did

- To predict the fatigue failure of unidirectional CFRP, we introduced entropy-based damage criterion into the SFF model.

Experiment Conditions

- Matrix : T300/Epoxy
- $f = 2$ Hz
- $R = 0.1$

Result

- The results suggest that fatigue failure of unidirectional composites can be predicted based on the degradation of matrix strength.

Experimental and analytical fatigue strength of CFRP strand against the number of cycles to failure

Motivation

For ensuring safety in long-term use, it is important to evaluate not only static strength but also fatigue characteristics

Numerical simulations to clarify the fatigue characteristics of CFRP is needed

Backgrounds

- There are few studies that takes numerical approach
 - It is hard to conduct large-scale experiments for component design, yet experimental approaches are mainstream.

Suggestion

- Predicting fatigue failure using entropy as an indicator
 - Focusing on entropy enables numerical simulations of fatigue life and residual strength after fatigue.
 - **Incorporating the entropy-based damage criterion into the SFF model for predicting the strength of unidirectional CFRP enables the prediction of its fatigue strength.**

Knowing the entropy allows for the prediction of fatigue failure even under variable or interrupted loading conditions.

SFF model

Average stress of fiber

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = (1 - q')E_f\varepsilon + \frac{qE_f\varepsilon}{2}$$

The probability of fiber break

$$q' = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{2nL_r'}{L_0} \left(\frac{E_f\varepsilon}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad \text{weakest-link theory}$$

Stress recovery length

$$L_r' = \frac{E_f\varepsilon D}{4\tau_0} \cdot n \sqrt{\frac{V_f}{V_f + n - 1}}$$

$$\cong \frac{E_f\varepsilon D}{4\tau_0} \sqrt{V_f n} \quad (\text{when } 1 \ll n)$$

Maximum fiber average stress

The maximum strength and critical strain of the fiber can be estimated by calculating $\frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_f}{\partial \varepsilon} = 0$

Fiber failure propagation

- n : The number of simultaneous fiber failures
- E_f : Elastic modulus of fiber
- V_f : Fiber volume fraction
- D : Diameter of fiber
- τ_0 : Interfacial shear strength
- L_0, σ_0, m : Weibull parameters

Jun Koyanagi, Hiroshi Hatta, Masaki Kotani and Hiroyuki Kawada, A comprehensive model for determining tensile strengths of various unidirectional composites, Journal of COMPOSITE MATERIALS, Vol.43, No. 18/2009

SFF model

Maximum stress

$$S'_{max} = S_c \frac{m+1}{m+2} \left(\frac{2}{m+2} \cdot \frac{1}{n^2} \sqrt{\frac{V_f + n - 1}{V_f}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}}$$

$$\cong S_c \frac{m+1}{m+2} \left(\frac{2}{m+2} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_f \cdot n^3}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \quad (\text{when } 1 \ll n)$$

Where $S_c = \left(\frac{2\sigma_0^m \tau_0 L_0}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}}$

Critical strain

$$\varepsilon'_{cri} = \frac{S_c}{E_f} \left(\frac{2}{m+2} \cdot \frac{1}{n^2} \sqrt{\frac{V_f + n - 1}{V_f}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}}$$

$$\cong \frac{S_c}{E_f} \left(\frac{2}{m+2} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{V_f + n^3}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}} \quad (\text{when } 1 \ll n)$$

The number of simultaneous fiber failures

$$\ln(n) = \alpha \cdot \ln\left(\frac{\tau_i}{\sqrt{\sigma_m \sigma_0}}\right) + \beta \quad (n > 1)$$

$$\alpha = 4.2, \beta = 12.6$$

σ_m : Matrix strength

Relationship between n and $\frac{\tau_i}{\sqrt{\sigma_m \sigma_0}}$ in various composites

The objective of this study

Issues with the SFF theory

- Considers σ_m (matrix strength) as a constant
 - The matrix strength is unknown both after loading, during loading, and when the load is altered midway
 - Not applicable to fatigue prediction

Suggestion

- Introduce the entropy-damage criterion into the SFF model
 - Reduce σ_m according to entropy generation
 - Applicable to fatigue prediction

Our goal

- Reproduce the S–N Curve from the Literature Using the SFF Model and Entropy-Based Damage Criterion

Experimental and analytical fatigue strength of CFRP strand against the number of cycles to failure

Entropy-based damage criterion

- Using Entropy as an indicator

When a load is applied, the order of the molecular arrangement is disturbed, and the entropy increases.

Entropy is not based on strain or stress, making it possible to consider irreversible cumulative damage.

- Merit

Entropy is not based on strain or stress, making it possible to consider irreversible cumulative damage.

Apply Entropy-Based damage criterion on Matrix

Relate the strength of CFRP after fatigue loading to the overall entropy of the CFRP.

Nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive law

Nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive law

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = (1 - D) \int_0^t E_{ijkl}^r(t - t') \frac{g d\epsilon_{kl}^{ve}}{dt'} dt'$$

E^r : Relaxation modulus
 D : Damage variable
 g : Nonlinear coefficient
 ϵ^{ve} : Viscoelastic strain

Relaxation modulus

$$E_{ijkl}^r(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{15} E_{ijkl}^n e^{-tE^n/\eta^n}$$

Nonlinear coefficient

$$g = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m}$$

Damage variable

$$D = D_v + D_e$$

E^n : Elastic modulus
 η^n : Viscosity coefficient
 σ_{eqv} : Equivalent stress
 α : Nonlinear parameter
 σ_0 : Specific stress
 m : Nonlinear exponent
 D_v : Damage variable (viscosity)
 D_e : Damage variable (elasticity)

Nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive law

Nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive law

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = (1 - D) \int_0^t E_{ijkl}^r(t - t') \frac{g d\varepsilon_{kl}^{ve}}{dt'} dt'$$

E^r : Relaxation modulus
 D : Damage variable
 g : Nonlinear coefficient
 ε^{ve} : Viscoelastic strain

Entropy (viscosity)

$$\Delta s_v(i) = \sum_{j=1}^{15} \frac{\sigma_{temp}(i, j) + \sigma(i, j)}{2} \cdot \frac{\Delta b}{T}$$

$$s_v = s_{v \text{ old}} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta s_v(i)$$

Damage variable (viscosity)

$$D_v = s_v \cdot \frac{D_{cr}}{S_{cr}}$$

Entropy (elasticity)

$$\Delta s_e(i) = \frac{E(j) \cdot \Delta D_v \cdot \Delta a^2(i, j)}{2 \cdot T}$$

$$s_e = s_{e \text{ old}} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta s_e(i)$$

Damage variable (viscosity)

$$D_e = s_e \cdot \frac{D_{cr}}{S_{cr}}$$

σ_{temp} : Temporally stress
 Δb : Dashpot deformation
 Δa : Spring deformation
 T : Absolute temperature
 D_{cr} : Critical damage
 S_{cr} : Critical entropy

UMAT computational flow

Entropy (viscosity)

$$\Delta s_v(i) = \sum_{j=1}^{15} \frac{\sigma_{temp}(i,j) + \sigma(i,j)}{2} \cdot \frac{\Delta b}{T}$$

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Damage variable (viscosity)

$$D_e = s_e \cdot \frac{D_{cr}}{S_{cr}}$$

Relationship between matrix residual strength and entropy

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Conceptual illustration of loading on a single-element model

Constitutive Relationship Between Entropy and Matrix Residual Strength

$$\sigma_m = \left(1 - \left(\frac{s}{s_{cr}}\right)^a\right)^{\frac{1}{b}} \quad s_{cr} = 1000, a = 1.3, b = 5$$

Matrix resin

- Nonlinear viscoelastic model
- Analysis algorithm was implemented using the Abaqus/Standard user subroutine

Analysis using the SFF model

The maximum strength of fiber and entropy

The maximum fiber strength in composite

$$S'_{max} = S_c \frac{m+1}{m+2} \left(\frac{2}{m+2} \cdot \frac{1}{n^2} \sqrt{\frac{V_f + n - 1}{V_f}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m+1}}$$

$$\ln(n) = \alpha \cdot \ln\left(\frac{\tau_i}{\sqrt{\sigma_m \sigma_0}}\right) + \beta \quad (n > 1)$$

$$\sigma_m = \left(1 - \left(\frac{s}{s_{cr}} \right)^m \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

The model parameters such as the Weibull parameters are calibrated to ensure that the maximum fiber strength at each temperature corresponds to the experimental values

Analysis using the SFF model

- ① Fracture is assumed to occur at the point where the residual strength curve (blue line) intersects with the applied stress amplitude (red line)
 - ② The entropy at the time of fracture is extracted.
 - ③ The entropy at fracture is converted into the number of fatigue cycles.
- The relationship between entropy and the number of fatigue cycles depends on the stress amplitude.
 - For each stress amplitude, determine the functional relationship between entropy and the number of cycles.

Convert using the relationship:
“Number of cycles = function of entropy”

Result

- It was demonstrated that fatigue failure prediction is possible by introducing the entropy-based damage criterion into the SFF model.
- This allows for the prediction of residual strength and the number of cycles to failure

Experimental and analytical fatigue strength of CFRP strand against the number of cycles to failure

Summary

- We introduced the entropy-failure criterion into the SFF model
- The result shows that the SFF model can predict fatigue failure of unidirectional reinforced composite materials.